
Evaluating the Nutritional Composition of Dried Pasta Available in Supermarkets

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Abstract

The variation in nutritional composition across dried pasta available from main supermarkets and how the difference or variation have impact on nutritional quality of the pasta, was analysed in this study. Aim of this study is to evaluate the price and nutritional composition difference between whole wheat pasta and white pasta from retailers. The data of Price (£) and nutritional composition such as Fibre(g), Protein(g), Carbohydrate(g), Fat(g), Energy(kcal), Sugar(g), Salt(g) and Saturates(g) of White pasta and Whole wheat pasta in Fusilli, Spaghetti and Penne shape from top five retailers was collected and analysed. The results of this study showed that fibre content was comparatively high in whole wheat pasta (mean of 4.8g/100g) and among the five retailers, fibre content was high in Morrisons pasta (mean of 3.5g/100g), and Sainsbury's (mean of 3.5g/100g) pasta comparatively. White pasta was rich in Protein, Carbohydrate, Fat, and Sugar content. On the other hand, whole wheat pasta was richer in fibre and salt content. The product price of White pasta was higher than Whole wheat pasta and Sainsbury's pasta was more expensive comparatively. As a conclusion, significant variation or difference is evident between nutritional values of White pasta and Whole wheat pasta across Retailers.

Acronym: g- gram, kcal- kilocalorie, the UK- the United Kingdom

1. Introduction

Pasta has traced origin from centuries (Webb 2019). History of pasta roots from several continents and cultures such as from middle east to Africa to Asia, which gets back to approximately 3500 years. In spite of various shapes and texture of pasta, it is universally connected to Italy (2). Due to arrival of Italian immigrants, the pasta was introduced in United Kingdom in 19th century and early period of 20th century (Ferdinando Pastore, director of the Italian Trade Agency). However, first production of pasta has emerged in 1936 at the UK. It has also taken 20 more years to start first pasta restaurant in London (17). The 68% of Britain's intake pasta once per week at least and more than once in a week by 42% of population (3), this shows the popularity of pasta in United Kingdom. Nowadays, refined or white flour are enriched with the nutrients, i.e., addition of iron and vitamin B after flour or grain processing, but may not Fibre (American Heart Association 2021). Refined and milled grains (germ and bran removed) will have high glycemic index compared to whole grains that are processed (Harvard School of Public Health 2021). Pasta is made using Durum Wheat Semolina. There is a decreed or order that the dried pasta should be manufactured from durum wheat in many countries such as Greece, France, and Italy (Sisson M,2008). From the previous study or research works, pasta that have higher carbohydrate content will lead to better nutritional pattern (Webb 2019 p:216). Consumption of whole grain pasta along low fat components or ingredients and minimum intake of 30 grams dietary Fibre per day is recommended, which may reduce the risk of numerous diseases related to nutrition (Gonzalez Fischer C and Garnett T. 2016. p:18).

The previous study "Nutritional Quality of Pasta Sold on the Italian Market: The Food Labelling of Italian Products (FLIP) Study" shows the nutritional composition of the current various types of pasta that are sold in markets of Italy, comparing the salt, energy, and nutrient content in dried and fresh pasta per 100 gram and compare the declaration of nutrition in products without and with various declarations such as nutrition claims, organic and gluten free (Dello Russo, Spagnuolo et al. 2021).

The Aim of the current study is to Evaluate the price, nutritional composition especially Fibre and comparing across various categories such as white and whole wheat pasta from main retailers in the UK. The purpose of this study is to highlight the difference (variation) in nutritional composition between different types of pasta (white pasta and whole grain pasta) across various supermarkets or retailers. The Main Objective of this study:

1. To evaluate the price and nutritional composition difference between whole wheat pasta and white pasta from retailers.
2. To analysis statistically and compare the price, contents of nutrients especially fibre in white pasta and whole wheat pasta of different brands available from retailers.
3. To determine the interquartile range and average mean of nutritional composition, price, white pasta, whole wheat pasta, and retailers.
4. To analyse the variation of Nutritional composition across various Brand, Retailer, Pasta shape, Pasta Type, Product size, and Nutritional contents.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1.Data Collection from Retailer's websites

2.1.1 Retailers and Pasta Selection

Initially, two types of pasta were chosen, one is white pasta and other is whole wheat pasta. The pasta types were selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria: Dried pasta, White pasta, Whole wheat pasta, Fusilli pasta, Spaghetti pasta, Penne Pasta

Exclusion criteria: Fresh pasta, Rigatoni Pasta, Conchiglie Pasta Shell, Spirali Pasta, Farfalle Pasta, Linguine Pasta, Tagliatelle Pasta, Quick Cook Fusilli Pasta, Packet pasta, Red Lentil Pasta, Ready to eat Pasta Pots, Pre-cooked Pasta and Cooked Pasta, not available at website during data information collection, incomplete ingredients list and unfinished images of package.

2.1.2 Online search and search protocol

The online websites of selected five retailers was accessed and searched pasta according to the search protocol:

- Entered as "pasta" in search column of website
- Then filtered out "Dried pasta"
- Next filtered white pasta and whole wheat pasta
- Extracted all the required data from the nutritional composition table of selected pasta.

All of the above steps were carried out in each website of five retailers. The data were gathered from the table of nutritional compositions per 100gram and price per 500gram. Consistently fusilli, spaghetti and penne shape pasta information was taken from each website for uniform or consistent

analysis. The search on online websites was carried out in June 2023. This study involved collection and analyses of data based on the nutrient content provided on the nutritional table of pasta products.

2.1.3 Excel spreadsheet

Data was collected from each websites and entered those information into a excel sheet which was categorised by retailers, brand name, name of the product, pasta type, pasta shape, product size (500gram), product price (per 500gram), fibre (gram), protein (gram), carbohydrate (gram), fat (gram), sugar (gram), energy (kcal), salt (gram) and saturates (gram). Entered the corresponding values under each category in the excel sheet. The nutritional value or composition was presented by standard measures (in grams per 100gram) and product size of 500gram. All the prices listed and analysed in this study was based on the pricing of those products during the study was undertaken (June 2023).

2.2 Data Analysis

2.2.1 Pre-processing the data

Initially, the Data were not normally distributed, assessed by analysing the significance of the collected data from different retailers. Test of normality (significance test) was carried out using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The p-value < 0.05 was taken as cut-off for significance which means there will be $< 5\%$ chance for the result to occur at random. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used as it can easily analysis the distribution. The test results showed that nutritional values or composition and product price had $p < 0.001$, thus null hypothesis was rejected which represented that the results were significant. So, the data were represented using Mean and Interquartile range. Moreover, two non-parametric test (Mann-Whitney test and Kruskal Wallis test) was used. Further to check the white pasta and whole wheat pasta value differences, Mann-Whitney test was used and to test the value differences of pasta across five retailers, Kruskal Wallis test was used.

2.2.2 Statistical Analysis of data

A Descriptive statistical analysis was performed by using SPSS Software (SPSS Statistics, 28.0) on the acquired data to show the understanding of the overall patterns, distributions, and trends in the nutritional composition of the white and whole wheat pasta types from five retailers. Therefore, estimated the Median, Interquartile range, Mean, Descriptive statistics, Standard Deviation of nutritional values. Analysis of comparison was carried out between white and whole wheat pasta to comprehend the difference in price and nutritional composition. Similarly, price and nutritional composition difference was analysed across five retailers. These analysis resulted in table of mean, 95% Confidence Interval for Mean, 5% Trimmed Mean, Median, Variance, Standard Deviation, Minimum value, Maximum value, Range, Interquartile Range, Skewness, Kurtosis and steam-leaf plot of price, and nutritional composition across retailers; a box plot of price and nutritional composition (Fibre, Protein, Carbohydrate, Fat, Sugar, Energy, Salt and Saturates) across white pasta, and whole wheat pasta.

3. Results

In this study, totally fifty eight pasta products (n=58) across five retailers were chosen to analyse. In which, forty one products were white pasta (n=41) and seventeen was whole wheat pasta (n=17). Where twenty was fusilli shaped pasta (n=20), twenty one was spaghetti shaped pasta (n=21), seventeen was penne shaped pasta (n=17).

3.1. Analysis of nutritional composition and price

The product price and nutritional composition of forty one White pasta and seventeen Whole wheat pasta across five Retailers (Table 1) showed a huge amount of difference between energy and other nutritional compositions where salt was the least. It presented the overall mean of nutritional composition and price of white pasta and whole wheat pasta from different retailers. There was high or huge variation between energy and other nutritional contents of white pasta and whole wheat pasta and also high variation in nutritional composition and price of white pasta and whole wheat pasta across retailers while analyzed different pasta shapes among each pasta category. On comparison of nutritional composition, whole wheat pasta had high salt(g) and fibre(g) content than white pasta. However, white pasta had high protein(g), carbohydrate(g), energy(kcal), saturates(g), fat(g) and sugar(g) content. In comparison of retailers, there was significant inconsistency in nutritional composition between the five retailers. Retailer Sainsbury's had the highest fibre content, but salt content was less when compared to other nutritional composition of Sainsburys.

3.2. key findings

The Table 1 provides the Mean value of nutritional composition, price, white pasta and whole wheat pasta, retailers such as Aldi, Asda, Morrisons, Sainsburys, Tesco and interquartile range. The results of Table 1 showed that mean of energy(kcal) levels per 100 grams ranged from 190 kcal to 289 kcal. The fibre content ranged from 2.6 gram to 4.8 gram per 100 gram and whole wheat pasta had higher content of fibre in comparison with white pasta. The fibre content was high in pasta of retailers such as Sainsbury's and Morrisons. The protein content was lowest in Aldi's pasta with 7.1g/100g (5.6g-9.2g) mean value whereas, high in Sainsbury's pasta with 10.3g/100g (5.5g-14.0g) mean value and white pasta had higher protein content of 10.3g/100g (5.3g-14.0g) mean value whereas, whole wheat pasta had low protein content of 6.6g/100g (4.8g-13.0g) median value. The carbohydrate content was high in white pasta with 59.3g/100g(31.0g-72.0g) mean value whereas, whole wheat pasta was least with 37.8g/100g (28.0g-65.50g) mean value and Aldi's pasta had more carbohydrate content with 58.6g/100g (31.0g-71.0g) mean value and least was Asda's pasta with 43.7g/100g (28.0g-72.0g) mean value. The fat content was less in Aldi and Asda with 1.0g/100g (0.6g-1.45g) and 1.0g/100g (0.6g-1.5g) mean value respectively whereas, fat content was more in Morrisons pasta with 1.5g/100g (1.5g-2.5g) mean value and white pasta has higher fat content with mean value of 1.3g/100g (0.6g-2.0g) whereas, whole wheat pasta has low fat content with mean value of 1.2g/100g(0.7g-2.5g).

3.3. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

The Kolmogorov- Smirnov results illustrated that the p-value(significance) of product price, fibre, protein, carbohydrate, fat, sugar, energy, salt and saturates were less than 0.001(p-value < 0.001) i.e., the p-value of the price and nutritional composition was less than 0.05(cutoff p-value <0.05). Thus, null hypothesis was rejected which indicates that the results were significant.

3.4. Mann-Whitney test

The value difference between the white pasta and whole wheat pasta was checked using Mann-Whitney test. The test results showed that the Product Price (£), Fibre (g), Protein (g), Carbohydrate (g), Sugar (g), Energy (kcal) and Salt (g) across white pasta and whole wheat pasta had $p < 0.05$ (p -value < 0.05 was taken as cutoff) and rejected the null hypothesis. Thus, the values were significant. However, the fat(g) and saturates(g) had significance level(p -value) greater than 0.05(cutoff value), retained the null hypothesis. So, the values were not significant.

3.5. Kruskal Wallis test

The value difference of pasta across five retailers was tested using Kruskal Wallis test. The test results showed that the Product price (£), Fibre (g), Protein (g), Carbohydrate (g), and Energy (kcal) across white pasta and whole wheat pasta had $p > 0.05$ (p -value < 0.05 was taken as cutoff) and retained the null hypothesis. So, the values were not significant. However, the Fat(g), Sugar(g), Salt(g) and Saturates(g) had significance level(p -value) less than 0.05(cutoff value) and rejected the null hypothesis. Thus, the values were significant.

Figure 1 represents the box plot of price and nutritional composition across white and whole wheat pasta. 'A' shows the box plot of Product price (£) across white and whole wheat pasta. 'B' represents the Fibre content(g) across white and whole wheat pasta. 'C' shows the Protein(g) content across white and whole wheat pasta. 'D' shows the Carbohydrate(g) across two pastas (white and whole wheat pasta). 'E' shows the Fat(g) content across two types of pasta. 'F' represents the Sugar(g) content across two pastas. 'G' represents the Energy(kcal) across two pasta types. 'H' shows the Salt(g) across two pastas. 'I' shows the Saturates(g) across white and whole wheat pasta.

Figure 2 shows the results of Mann-Whitney U test, tested to nutritional value or composition difference between the white pasta and whole wheat pasta. 'A' represents the mean rank and average (Avg) frequency of Product price (£) across white pasta and whole wheat pasta. 'B' shows the mean rank and Avg frequency

of Fibre(g) across two pastas. 'C' shows the mean rank and average frequency of Protein(g) across two pastas. 'D' shows the mean rank and Avg.frequency of Carbohydrate(g) across two pasta types. 'E' shows the mean rank and Avg.frequency of Fat(g) across two pasta. 'F' shows the mean rank and frequency of Sugar(g) across two pastas. 'G' shows the mean rank and Avg.frequency of Energy(kcal) across two pasta. 'H' shows the mean rank and Avg. frequency of Salt(g) across two pasta wheat pasta. 'I' represents the mean rank and Avg. frequency of Saturates(g) across white pasta and whole wheat pasta.

Table1 represents Mean value of Nutritional Composition, Price, White Pasta, and Whole Wheat Pasta, Retailers and Interquartile Range

Nutrients	Mean	White pasta	Whole Wheat pasta	Aldi	Asda	Morrisons	Sainsburys	Tesco
Price(£)	1.14 (0.75-2.0)	1.25 (0.75-2.0)	0.90 (0.75-1.47)	0.92 (0.75-1.17)	0.83 (0.75-1.0)	1.16 (0.99-1.55)	1.30 (0.75-2.0)	1.25 (0.75-2.0)
Fibre(g)	3.2 (1.5-8.0)	2.6 (1.49-3.0)	4.8 (3.3-8.5)	2.7 (1.40-3.30)	2.9 (2.1-3.7)	3.5 (2.90-8.0)	3.5 (1.5-6.41)	3.0 (2.2-3.8)
Protein(g)	9.2 (4.8-14.0)	10.3 (5.3-14.0)	6.6 (4.8-13.0)	7.1 (5.6-9.2)	7.4 (4.8-12.0)	9.8 (12.0-14.0)	10.3 (5.5-14.0)	9.3 (5.4-14.0)
Carbohydrate(g)	53 (28.0-72.0)	59.3 (31.0-72.0)	37.8 (28.0-65.50)	58.6 (31.0-71.0)	43.7 (28.0-72.0)	54.4 (64.0-72.0)	55.5 (29.5-72.0)	52.4 (32.9-72)
Fat(g)	1.3 (0.60-2.17)	1.3 (0.6-2.0)	1.2 (0.7-2.5)	1.0 (0.6-1.45)	1.0 (0.6-1.5)	1.5 (1.5-2.5)	1.4 (0.7-2.0)	1.1 (0.7-1.5)
Sugar(g)	2.1 (0.50-3.50)	2.4 (0.5-3.5)	1.4 (0.5-3.5)	1.6 (0.8-2.15)	1.3 (0.5-3.0)	2.6 (3.0-3.5)	2.3 (0.7-3.5)	2.2 (1.10-3.4)
Energy(Kcal)	260 (147-359)	289 (155-359)	190 (147-347)	198 (159-256.5)	219 (147-356)	277 (347-359)	283 (164-359)	263 (168-356)
Salt(g)	0.019 (0.0-0.08)	0.016(0.0-0.8)	0.03 (0.01-0.08)	0.014 (0.0-0.03)	0.023 (0.01-0.03)	0.009 (0.0-0.013)	0.008 (0.0-0.01)	0.043 (0.0-0.08)
Saturates(g)	0.3 (0.1-0.5)	0.3(0.1-0.5)	0.3 (0.2-0.5)	0.3 (0.2-0.4)	0.2 (0.1-0.3)	0.3 (0.3-0.5)	0.3 (0.2-0.5)	0.3 (0.2-0.3)

(-)-The values inside the brackets indicates the interquartile range

Table 2 shows the median value of nutritional composition, price across five retailers and two types of pasta

Nutrients	Aldi	Asda	Morrisons	Sainsburys	Tesco	White	Whole Wheat
Price (£)	0.75	0.75	1.39	1.4	1.12	1.4	0.75
Fibre(g)	3.1	3	3	3	2.95	2.95	3.8
Protein(g)	5.7	5.3	13	12	8.9	12	5.7
Carbohydrate(g)	67	31	71	69	52.3	71	31.95
Fat(g)	0.7	0.9	1.75	1.5	1.15	1.5	0.9
Sugar(g)	1.4	0.5	3.45	3	2.05	3	1.1
Energy (Kcal)	161	155	356	351	263.5	351	164
Salt(g)	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.013
Saturates(g)	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.25	0.3	0.2

4.Discussion

This study shows the nutritional value of various pasta products available from different retailers of United Kingdom. The findings depict the price difference, and nutritional difference in pasta across top retailers of the UK. Pricing depends on quality of the product, market trends, branding or marketing and ingredients. The results of nutritional values show the differences in nutrients and

price across two types of pasta categories, i.e., white pasta and whole wheat pasta and the significance of these values are tested by Mann-Whitney test (Figure 2). In this study, White pasta shows a higher Protein, Carbohydrate, Fat, Energy, Sugar, Saturates and a lesser Fibre, and Salt content respectively when compared to others. As white pasta is made up of refined wheat flour (Durum Wheat Semolina), these kinds of difference are observed. Thus, high amount of carbohydrate and protein gives the energy content(kcal) to pasta. The salt content depends on retailer or manufacturer. Usually, traditional white pasta has low saturate content (Fry et al. 2018). On the other hand, whole wheat pasta shows a higher salt, and fibre content and a lower saturates, protein, carbohydrate, fat, sugar, energy content respectively in comparison to white pasta. Fibre content is high in whole wheat pasta as bran outer layer in kernel is a good source of fibre. Generally, Whole wheat has higher content of fat as the germ part of the wheat kernel comprises natural oils, which causes to have high content of fat. However, in this study, the fat content was less than white pasta. The saturate content is low in whole wheat pasta which means they have healthy fat contents, due to germ's natural oils that comprises unsaturated fats. On the other hand, white pasta lacks germ so they might have high saturates. By nature, whole wheat pasta may have slightly higher protein content when compared to white pasta, due to germ in whole wheat. However, in this study, the whole wheat pasta has less protein content than white pasta, low protein content is due to processing of pasta or usage of wheat type. Pasta's energy content (kcal) is obtained from (or) based on contents of Fat, Protein, and Carbohydrate. Here, whole wheat pasta has low energy content(kcal). However, in this study, there are slight variations in protein content across the different retailers i.e., Aldi have higher protein content and Tesco, Asda, Morrisons, Sainsburys have slightly low protein content. As mentioned in the introduction, the Previous study "Nutritional Quality of Pasta Sold on the Italian Market: The Food Labelling of Italian Products (FLIP) Study", analyzed 756 products from 13 retailers and the result of this study indicates that in fresh pasta, the egg pasta had higher energy content of 293 kcal/100 g than stuffed pasta (274 kcal/100g) and semolina pasta (272 kcal/100g). Dried pasta, egg pasta had energy level of 369 kcal/100g and stuffed pasta had 394 kcal/100g which is higher than semolina with energy of 354 kcal/100g and special pasta with 351 kcal/100g (Dello Russo.M et al.,2021). However, in this study, energy level of white pasta (dried pasta) is high with 289 kcal/100g than whole wheat pasta (dried pasta) with 190 kcal/100g. In pervious study, the carbohydrate content was abundant and energy ranged from 54% in stuffed fresh pasta and 71% in semolina dried pasta (Dello Russo.M et al.,2021). However, this study, the carbohydrate content is more in white pasta (dried pasta) and less in whole wheat pasta (dried pasta). Naturally, pasta have less salt content (Webb, D. 2019. p:214). The two-oz (56.70g) dry serving or amount of whole wheat pasta gives 25% of required fibre for daily consumption (Webb, D. 2019. p:214). In this current study, the whole wheat pasta had more fibre content of 4.8g/100g (mean value) than white pasta with 2.6g/100g (mean value). The choice of either choosing white pasta or whole wheat pasta depends on each particular person and their dietary requirements. If the requirement or choice is high fibre content, may choose whole wheat pasta or if choice of an individual is taste than health or dietary concern, may choose white pasta. The further work suggestions are analysis or meta analysis of fibre content in white pasta across whole wheat pasta and gut health effects, a analysis or systematic review on impact of pasta intake in health issues such as diabetes, obesity, rate of mortality and cardiovascular diseases, Study on opinions of consumers about health gains and taste opinions on white pasta and whole wheat or whole grain pasta and systematic study or data analysis of evaluating micronutrient contents such as minerals, iron, vitamins, zinc &c.contents of different types of pasta.

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the nutritional composition such as Fibre (g), Protein (g), Carbohydrate (g), Fat (g), Energy (kcal), Sugar (g), Salt (g) and Saturates (g) Content and Price of white pasta and whole wheat pasta in fusilli, spaghetti and penne shaped pasta from top five retailers such as Tesco, Asda, Aldi, Sainsbury's and Morrisons. The key result of this study shows that white pasta is a major source of instant energy, as white pasta has high energy content and carbohydrate content. Comparatively, Fibre and Fat content is significantly high in whole wheat pasta than white pasta. The minor differences in contents of fibre, energy, fat, sugar, salt, saturates, protein and carbohydrates across various retailers and brand, emphasize the requirement of go-through or reading of the pasta products labels to ensure the right choice of pasta product with required nutrients. The results of this study correspond the values of nutrients are nutritional values in grams per 100g of the total product size. Nutritional composition such as Fibre(g), Protein(g), carbohydrate(g), Fat(g), Sugar(g), Energy(g), Salt(g), and Saturates(g) are high in whole wheat pasta than white pasta comparatively. In comparison of pastas of five retailers such as Tesco, Aldi, Morrisons, Asda and Sainsbury's nutritional composition, Sainsbury's and Morrisons have higher composition of values. In price comparison, white pasta was comparatively expensive than whole wheat pasta and retailer Sainsbury's pasta is expensive than others comparatively.

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